

The Tapping Orchestra: A 10-Person Platform for Measuring Behavioral & Neural Synchrony During Group Interaction

Anna Zamm^{a,b*}, Simon L. Kappel^{c,d*}, Alexander P. Demos^e, Stefan Debener^f, Ivana Konvalinka^g

*Denotes joint first authors

^aDepartment of Linguistics, Cognitive Science and Semiotics, Aarhus University, Denmark

^bInteracting Minds Center, Aarhus University, Denmark

^cDepartment of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Aarhus University, Denmark

^dCenter for Ear-EEG, Aarhus University, Denmark

^eDepartment of Psychology, University of Illinois Chicago, USA

^fDepartment of Psychology, University of Oldenburg, DE

^gSection for Cognitive Systems, DTU Compute, Technical University of Denmark, Denmark

Corresponding authors:

Anna Zamm (azamm@cc.au.dk, Phone: +45 27 21 72 67)

Jens Chr. Skous Vej 2, Building 1485, Room 626, 8000 Aarhus C, Denmark

Simon Lind Kappel (slk@ece.au.dk, Phone: +45 20 69 34 56)

Finlandsgade 22, Building 5125, Room 329, 8200 Aarhus N, Denmark

Abstract

Group synchrony — the temporal coordination of rhythmic behaviors between multiple individuals — is fundamental to human social interaction. Although synchrony often occurs in large groups such as orchestras or sports teams, most scientific knowledge comes from investigating dyads, typically in joint music-making contexts. Scaling investigation beyond the dyad presents significant methodological challenges, including building measurement platforms that simultaneously acquire data from many individuals and developing paradigms that can be systematically scaled across n -person groups. Here we present "The Tapping Orchestra", a low-latency platform for measuring group synchrony at brain (EEG) and behavioral levels during musical interaction. Accessible to both musicians and non-musicians, participants tap sensors to produce successive tones in a melody, enabling the experience of music production without learning complex auditory sequences. We describe the platform's design, implementation, and validation of measurement accuracy for hardware and software. We report findings from a proof-of-concept study adapting an established dyadic synchronization paradigm to larger groups, demonstrating the platform's scalability for measuring synchrony across diverse group sizes. Together, technical and empirical validation of The Tapping Orchestra establishes a methodological foundation for investigating how coordination dynamics scale to larger group behavior, paving the way for systematic approaches to multi-person neuroscience.

Keywords: Social interaction, hyperscanning, group synchrony, joint action

Highlights

- “The Tapping Orchestra” measures group synchrony from up to 10-persons
- Systematically extends dyadic finger-tapping to larger groups
- Low latency simultaneous acquisition of multi-brain EEG and tapping data
- Scalability for n -person groups validated through proof-of-concept study
- Paves the way for systematic approaches to investigating groups

1 Introduction

Group synchrony — the temporal coordination of rhythmic behaviors between multiple individuals — is fundamental to human social interaction (Hoehl et al., 2021), from group music-making (Abalde et al., 2024; Keller et al., 2014) to team sports (Tamminen et al., 2023) and myriad forms of joint action (Sebanz & Knoblich, 2021). Despite the ubiquity of large group interaction in our social lives, scientific investigation of synchrony since the early days of joint action research (Sebanz et al., 2006) has focused almost exclusively on dyadic (two-person) interaction. The "two-brain approach" (Konvalinka & Roepstorff, 2012; Schilbach et al., 2013) arose in the early 2000s, representing a critical paradigm shift from traditional approaches that measured individuals' responses to computerized "social" stimuli outside any natural social context. Two-brain neuroscience has since advanced our understanding of interacting minds, allowing for scientists to study social behavior as embedded within a dynamical system, where reciprocal influences of self- and other- modulate neural signals and behavior (Heggli et al., 2021; Konvalinka et al., 2023; Konvalinka et al., 2025; Konvalinka et al., 2010).

Although the two-brain approach has been invaluable for uncovering mechanisms of dyadic social interaction, it must not represent an endpoint for synchrony research. Larger groups can present far greater coordination challenges than two-person interaction. The number of possible pairwise interactions within groups increases exponentially with group size (Demos & Palmer, 2023), quickly exceeding human attentional capacity (Marois & Ivanoff, 2005). Consequently, mechanisms that enable successful coordination with a single partner must be adapted or changed when the number of partners exceeds attentional limits, with implications for diverse group behaviors from conversation to music-making to sports. This scaling problem suggests that groups may require fundamentally different coordination strategies - such as hierarchical organization, attention to global timing cues, or role specialization - that are not consistently required in dyadic contexts. Although some work has addressed synchrony in groups larger than two (for a review see Gordon, 2025), there is no clear consensus among social neuroscientists regarding a coherent theoretical or empirical framework for investigating how dyadic synchronization dynamics scale to larger groups (A. P. Demos & C. Palmer, 2023; Alexander P. Demos & Caroline Palmer, 2023; Keller, 2023).

1.1 Music-making as a model system for measuring group synchrony

Music-making affords an ideal model system for developing coherent theoretical and empirical frameworks of synchrony, particularly because many mechanisms of dyadic interaction have been identified through joint music-making paradigms (Abalde et al., 2024; Keller et al., 2014). Musical coordination scales naturally from dyads to large ensembles — from small chamber groups to orchestras with hundreds of musicians. Music exists in all cultures with varying levels of training, enabling investigation of how individual skill and expertise affect synchronization with others. Although music has unique features such as pitch perception and instrument-specific motor skills that may not generalize to other forms of group synchrony (e.g., team sports, dance), generating and maintaining predictable actions — a core feature of music —

underpins synchronization across coordination domains (Sebanz et al., 2006), making insights from music-making invaluable.

The core feature of music that enables prediction and synchronization is the *beat*, a regular pulse around which musical actions are organized. Musical tones are typically aligned with the beat and its subdivisions, and people can perceive the beat of music regardless of whether they have musical training (Grahn & Rowe, 2009). Musicians naturally manipulate the beat, suspending it during expressive pauses between phrases or destabilizing it when speeding up or slowing down (Palmer, 1997). These natural manipulations of beat — which can also be experimentally manipulated — allow for investigating how rhythmic structure facilitates coordination and how synchronization is maintained when rhythm falls away, as commonly occurs in other coordination domains like team sports or conversational speech, which do not possess such clearly defined rhythmic structures as music.

Although not all people can play musical instruments, a vast body of literature shows that the ability to maintain and synchronize with a beat can be experimentally isolated and measured in the general population — in musicians and nonmusicians alike — using rhythmic finger-tapping paradigms (Repp, 2006; Repp & Su, 2013). In these paradigms, people tap musical rhythms on a drum or other surface, either solo or synchronized with an external rhythm such as an audio recording or live partner, and their tap timing is recorded. Much of what is known about timekeeping, rhythm production, and sensorimotor synchronization comes from these simple paradigms (for a review, see Repp & Su, 2013), making them ideal for scaling investigations from dyads to larger groups. Here we propose that the next step toward understanding group synchronization mechanisms is to adapt joint finger-tapping paradigms for larger groups.

1.2 Building a scalable music-making paradigm: Requirements & challenges

Scaling musical finger-tapping paradigms from dyads to larger groups introduces many methodological and theoretical challenges. First, synchronization studies require extremely low-latency measurement precision — often in the order of milliseconds — both within and between group members' recordings of behavioral, neural, physiological, and other biological signals. Specifically, many latencies must be controlled: action-outcome latencies within individuals must be kept low (e.g., tones generated by taps must be near instantaneous), and delays between subjects' data recordings in multiple modalities must be minimal. A given timestamp in one participant's data stream in one modality should correspond to the same timepoint in another participant's data in a different modality (Kappel et al., 2025). Achieving low latencies in dyads is challenging — in fact, it was only in the early 2000s that two-person hyperscanning entered mainstream scientific dialogue. Achieving low latencies in dyads is challenging — in fact, it was only in the early 2000s that two-person hyperscanning entered mainstream scientific dialogue (Montague et al., 2002). However, as group size increases, the challenge grows substantially due to potential network, hardware, and software bottlenecks, and these problems are not always solved through standard commercial hardware. Therefore, custom solutions are often required,

and the ability to precisely calibrate measurements is essential. Finally, platforms must be scalable to ensure that groups of varying sizes can be measured using identical technical set-ups.

1.3 “The Tapping Orchestra” approach

Here we present "The Tapping Orchestra," a novel low-latency platform for measuring group synchrony of up to 10 interacting participants using musical coordination as an empirical model. Building on prior work demonstrating that finger-tapping can be used as a paradigm for measuring timekeeping in the general population (Repp & Su, 2013) – musicians, non-musicians, adults, and children – the platform investigates behavioral synchrony through collective finger-tapping. Everyone in the tapping orchestra taps on an “instrument” that generates the next tone in a musical sequence, enabling everyone to produce musical rhythms without learning novel motor sequences. Group synchrony is achieved when all individuals align their taps to the same underlying rhythm, so that they occur simultaneously or with constant phase relations. The platform also measures multi-brain EEG synchronously with behavioral (tapping) recordings, allowing for investigating neural dynamics underlying behavioral synchrony.

We first describe how "The Tapping Orchestra" platform was designed, implemented, and tested for measurement accuracy regarding hardware and software, then describe a paradigm used to test the platform in a proof-of-concept study.

The paradigm used for our proof-of-concept study was adapted from work on dyadic synchronization [26], and contrasts group synchronization with and without musical rhythm, using unmetred silence between musical phrases as a model of rhythmic destabilization. This paradigm is ideal for investigating how rhythm affects synchronization across different group sizes, as it is readily scalable.

Our overarching aim is to provide a technical proof-of-concept demonstrating how social neuroscience can move toward systematic approaches to scaling beyond the dyad. Specifically, we introduce and validate a platform that enables low-latency, synchronized measurement of behavioral and neural activity during group interactions. Through this implementation and validation study, we illustrate how dyadic synchronization paradigms can be extended to larger groups, providing a methodological foundation for investigating how coordination dynamics scale from two individuals to larger ensembles.

2 Methods

2.1 The Tapping Orchestra Platform

“The Tapping Orchestra” platform was developed to measure synchronous tapping and EEG activity from groups of up to 10 individuals. To this end, we developed novel tapping “instruments” (sensors), hardware and software for recording taps, generating sound, and

synchronizing behavioral and EEG measurement. We describe in detail below how each of these platform features were developed, implemented and tested.

2.1.1 Design of tapping sensor

Ten custom tapping sensors with the same design were built for the "tapping orchestra", as shown in Figure 1. The sensor design was based on a force-sensing resistor (FSR; Interlink Electronics, FSR 406) operated at low current ($<5 \mu\text{A}$), ensuring negligible electromagnetic radiation to minimize artifacts in EEG recordings. The sensor provided immediate tactile feedback to each tap, ensuring that participants experienced a natural sensorimotor loop.

Each FSR sensor was mounted on a stable platform, as illustrated in Figure 1(a). The setup was equipped with an armrest to maintain a relaxed posture, reducing musculoskeletal fatigue during prolonged tapping sessions. In addition, the minimal actuation force of the FSR sensor (0.2 N) further reduced fatigue, which was necessary to maintain continuous measurements throughout the experiment. A shade cover was integrated above the tapping area to prevent participants from observing each other's finger movements, as shown in Figure 1(b), thereby minimizing confounds from visual cues about others' movements.

Figure 1. Custom hardware for tapping orchestra. (a) FSR based tapping sensor, (b) Tapping sensor with a cover to hide finger movements, (c) Custom Bela shield.

2.1.2 Hardware interface

The Bela low-latency audio platform (bela.io) was used to sample data from tapping sensors, generate associated auditory feedback, and send common synchronization triggers to each participant's EEG amplifier. The Bela is based on a BeagleBone Black embedded computer, running a Linux distribution with Xenomai real-time extensions, supporting hard real-time audio with time-locked digital I/O. Bela C++ code for the paper are available from ece.au.dk/tapping-orchestra.

2.1.2.1 Taps

The ten tapping sensors interfaced directly with the digital inputs of the BeagleBone Black via a custom shield designed specifically for the tapping orchestra (ece.au.dk/belashield), shown in Figure 2(c). The Bela supports sampling of these digital inputs together with the audio outputs, supporting low tap-to-audio latency. Comparator circuits (Schmitt triggers) on the shield featured

adjustable threshold and hysteresis settings, allowing fine-tuning of sensor sensitivity to tapping inputs.

2.1.2.2 Audio

The audio output associated with each tap was sampled with a Bela CTAG Beast Cape, a multichannel audio expansion board that extends Bela's output capacity to sixteen channels. Each tapping sensor was associated with an audio output, to create a spatial orientation of the audio, as described in the Experimental setup section. Rendering the audio and processing of the digital inputs/outputs were performed in frames of 16 samples with a sampling rate of 48 kHz, resulting in a frame processing frequency of 3 kHz.

2.1.2.3 Synchronization triggers

Trigger signals for synchronizing the paradigm with EEG data acquisition were generated by one of four digital outputs stages on the custom shield. The output was connected to a trigger distribution box, which provided galvanic isolation and converted the digital signal to a 5 V TTL trigger signal, as described in Kappel, Jørgensen and Kidmose (2025). The trigger signal was then distributed to the trigger input of all EEG amplifiers, enabling sample-level synchronization of tapping, audio, and EEG data. Manchester encoded triggers were sent with randomized inter-trigger intervals ranging from 500 to 1500 milliseconds to avoid phase alignment with tapping or audio feedback (Kappel et al., 2025).

2.1.2.4 External devices

The custom shield also featured an isolated UART-to-USB converter for galvanically isolated data communication with a laptop. This isolated connection enabled bidirectional transmission of control commands and status messages between the shield and a laptop running experimental control scripts.

2.1.3 Timing validation

2.1.3.1 Tap-to-audio

Tap-to-audio latency was measured by connecting a waveform generator to the sensor input and measuring the latency between tap input and audio generation with a digital oscilloscope. The waveform was a random digital signal, sampled at 200 Hz. 20 minutes of data from the oscilloscope was logged, and the latency from tap to audio generation was calculated in MATLAB R2023b. Mean latency was 1.43ms ($sd = 0.10ms$, $N = 70977$), representing the latency across all hardware and software layers of input (taps) and output (audio). Thus, the measured latency is smaller than the sampling period for frequencies up to approximately 700 Hz. Given that typical EEG sampling rates range from 250 to 512 Hz, the observed latency is sufficiently low and does not pose a problem for analyses of neural and behavioral synchrony.

2.1.3.2 Synchronization between sensors

Synchronization of audio produced by simultaneously tapped sensors was tested using a signal generator that created an artificial tap signal split between digital inputs on the custom shield.

Temporal offsets between audio output signals were subsequently measured using a digital oscilloscope. The mean temporal offset between sensors was 0.00ms ($sd = 0.01\text{ms}$, $N = 60040$).

2.1.3.3 Synchronization between Bela and EEG amplifiers

Temporal synchronization between the Bela and EEG amplifiers can be determined based on latencies between trigger times recorded by the Bela and EEG amplifiers. To determine the synchronization, we performed 20 recordings of more than 3000 triggers and considered the first transmitted trigger as time zero. The accumulated offset between the trigger time recorded by the Bela and EEG amplifiers were then calculated, and a linear fit was performed on the accumulated offsets from each recording, as shown in Figure 2. Based on the grand averaged slope of the linear fits, the analysis showed that windows of 129 seconds ($sd = 30$ seconds) of EEG data, can be analyzed without the synchronization drifting more than 1 EEG sample, at an EEG sampling rate of 500 Hz. If larger windows need to be analyzed, the accumulated offset can largely be corrected by resampling the EEG data to compensate for the sampling clock offset between the Bela and EEG amplifier. When corrected, the average offset was 0.00 samples ($sd = 0.30$ samples), suggesting a nearly perfect linear relationship between the sampling clock of the Bela and EEG amplifiers. In connection with the analysis 176 (0.0003 % of EEG samples) dropped EEG samples were identified and corrected.

Figure 2. Accumulated offset between the Bela and EEG amplifiers, measured in EEG samples at a sampling rate of 500 Hz. The faded lines are individual recordings, and the solid black line is the average linear fit.

2.2 Proof-of-concept study

A scalable paradigm of dyadic synchrony was adapted from (Zamm et al., 2021) and implemented in a validation study that featured a Main Experiment of synchrony in groups (4-, 6- and 10-person groups) and two Control Tasks. The following sections describe the participants, main experiment, and control tasks.

2.2.1 Participants

$N = 20$ participants (3 groups: 4-, 6- and 10-person) were included in the validation study. Prior to data collection, the study and recruitment procedures were approved by the Aarhus University (AU) Danish Neuroscience Center (DNC) Institutional Review Board (Case number: DNC-IRB-2022-010). Participants were recruited through the AU Center for Functionally Integrated Neuroscience (CFIN) SONA system. Stated recruitment criteria were 6+ years of formal musical training, right-handedness, no current neuropsychiatric medication and normal or corrected-normal vision. All participants provided informed written consent prior to participation and received gift vouchers of 450 DKK. One additional 10-person musician group completed the study but were discarded due to technical issues that prevented recording of the main experimental tasks. An additional 10-person group of non-musicians also completed the study, but are not included in validation analyses, as the focus of the validation study was on demonstrating validity of the paradigm with participants skilled in synchronization. Data was collected in a testing room in the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering at Aarhus University.

2.2.2 Main experiment

2.2.2.1 Design & Procedure

The Main Experiment required participants to tap a simple eight-tone melody in synchrony with their group. The number of trials matched group size (4, 6, or 10 trials for groups of 4, 6, or 10 members, respectively).

On each trial, one randomly selected member was assigned as Leader, with all others serving as Followers. The Leader maintained the rate established by an initial metronome and determined when to resume tapping after silences between melody iterations. Followers synchronized their taps with the Leader and anticipated when silences would end. Each member served as Leader once per condition.

Trials consisted of 20 melody iterations (8 tones each). Each began with a pacing cue: a computer-generated ascending-descending scale sequence with 800-ms inter-onset intervals (IOIs) and a 1600-ms silence (two IOIs) between ascending and descending portions. Auditory feedback from taps was enabled only after the pacing cue concluded. This procedure was adapted from a dyadic paradigm (Zamm et al., 2021).

Participants also completed a control group synchronization condition without visual contact and an individual tapping task, but we do not describe these tasks or report associated findings here as our focus is on validating the main group synchronization paradigm and platform.

2.2.2.2 Stimulus

Participants' taps produced a simple melody corresponding to a *c*-minor harmonic scale starting on C4 for Followers and C5 for Leaders, providing perceptual distinction between Leader and Follower tones. This scale was selected for its simplicity, familiarity, and raised

leading tone (B natural), which enhances harmonic resolution at the end of each ascending sequence.

As described above, Leaders were instructed to insert unmeasured silences (self-chosen duration) between the ascending and descending scale segments, creating temporal discontinuities that required Followers to predict when the Leader would resume tapping.

Each Leader tap advanced the scale sequence by one pitch, such that continuous tapping produced an ascending scale followed by a descending scale. Followers' taps always generated the same pitch as the Leaders' (one octave lower), controlling for auditory feedback across group members. Tones were sinusoidal, with a fixed duration of 100 ms and rise/fall times of 10ms.

Figure 3. Tone sequence (top) produced by participants' taps (middle). Tones progressed with each new tone produced by the Leader (bottom); each tone remained "active" (was assigned to all subsequent tones produced by all Followers) for a dynamically estimated time interval to ensure alignment of taps. This "active" interval was computed based on tap timing from the current tapping sequence (sub-indexed as 1 below) and the previous sequence (sub-indexed as 0 below). In the bottom panel, the active period for the third tone in melody sequence is based upon the average ITI of the previous sequence in addition to the average of the first two ITIs in the current sequence.

Tone progression algorithm. To align Followers' taps with the Leader's pitch despite timing asynchronies, each pitch remained "active" for a dynamic interval after the Leader's tap, as shown in Figure 3. This active interval, $t_{active}(n)$, was computed as follows:

$$t_{active}(n) = \frac{1}{4} \left[\left(\frac{1}{6} \sum_{i=2}^7 t_0(i) - t_0(i-1) \right) + \left(\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=2}^n t_1(i) - t_1(i-1) \right) \right]$$

where, $t_0(i)$ is the tap time for tone number i of the previous sequence, and $t_1(i)$ is the tap time for tone number i in the current sequence. The duration for which the tone was active for tap number 1 ($n = 1$) was not dynamically calculated but instead defined as $t_{active}(7)$ from the previous sequence. The eighth tone in the scale was excluded due to temporal irregularities before the silence observed during piloting.

To avoid unintended double-taps on the sensor, the sensor input was blocked for 100ms after each tap. Pilot participants reported a natural progression of the melody without pitch skips or delays.

2.2.3 EEG Auditory Steady State Response

Prior to the main experiment, participants were presented with a steady-state auditory stimulus designed to elicit an auditory steady-state response (ASSR). The stimulus was broadband white noise amplitude-modulated with a 40 Hz sinusoid at full modulation depth, presented monaurally via insert earphones at 65 dB SPL (Galambos et al., 1981). Participants kept their eyes closed during the 5-minute recording session.

The ASSR is a well-characterized response, which can be measured at locations all over the scalp (Picton et al., 2003). In the context of the present study, the ASSR was used to estimate if the electrode-skin interface of an electrode was good enough to measure a neural response. Thus, electrodes that did not measure an ASSR response could be discarded prior to analysis of EEG data from the main experiment (Kappel et al., 2019).

2.2.4 Experimental setup

Figure 4 illustrates the experimental setup. Participants were seated in chairs arranged in an oval configuration. Each participant had a tapping sensor positioned to their right and a speaker placed behind them to provide auditory feedback for their taps. Monitors for displaying instructions were placed on a low table (height: 15 cm) in the center, along with the Bela platform, described in the Hardware interface section. The top edge of the monitors was at 52 cm from the floor, allowing participants to maintain unobstructed visual contact with one another. EEG amplifiers were mounted to the back of participants' chairs.

Figure 4. Experimental setup. (a) and (b) Each participant had their own tapping sensor and speaker, along with EEG equipment. A trigger cable ran to the EEG amplifier to allow time synchronization of data from tapping, audio, and EEG. (c) and (d) In the center of the setup, monitors for instructions and the Bela platform, on which the paradigm was implemented. All participants consented to photos.

2.2.4.1 EEG

EEG data were continuously recorded from each participant using a TMSI Mobita 32-channel amplifier (Artinis Medical Systems BV) mounted on the back of participants' chairs. Electrodes were mounted in an EEG cap (Easycap GmbH) according to the extended 10-20 system, with measuring electrodes at locations Fp1, Fp2, F7, F3, Fz, F4, F8, FC5, FC1, FC2, FC6, T7, C3, Cz, C4, T8, M1, CP5, CP1, CP2, CP6, M2, P7, P3, Pz, P4, P8, O1, O2, and ground at CPz. In addition three EOG electrodes were mounted around the eyes: one positioned to the left of the left eye, one beneath the right eye, and one to the right of the right eye to capture horizontal and vertical ocular movements. All electrodes were 4mm Ag/AgCl with active shielding (Kappel & Kidmose, 2022) gelled with ECI Electro-Gel. Prior to the experiment, data quality were inspected visually, and gel was added to noisy electrodes. Trigger cables from the trigger

distribution box described in the Hardware interface section were carefully run across the floor to the each participants' EEG amplifier.

2.2.4.2 Audio setup

The speakers (Genelec 8020 DPM) positioned behind each participant were calibrated to deliver 65 dB SPL at 1kHz, using a free-field microphone (G.R.A.S. 46AF) placed approximately at the participants head position (40 cm from the speaker).

For the individual tapping and ASSR, the speakers were switched off, and audio was delivered through earphones instead. The earphones were custom-built EEG-compatible earphones with a 35 cm acoustic delivery tube placed between headphones (Sennheiser CX100) and ER3 foam eartips. The sound pressure of the earphones were calibrated to deliver 65 dB SPL at 1kHz using an Ear and Cheek Simulator with a large right KEMAR ear (simulator G.R.A.S. 43AG based on IEC 60318-4 & 7 and preamp G.R.A.S. 26AC).

For both the speaker and earphone calibrations, the SPL reference level was established using a 114 dB, 250 Hz pistonphone (G.R.A.S. 42AA).

2.2.4.3 Paradigm

The experimental paradigm was implemented in C++ on the Bela platform using custom-developed code together with Bela's core libraries. Data associated with triggers and taps from each participant (timestamps in audio samples, pitch generated, participant role, tap number, etc.) were continuously logged to files on the Bela. This logging architecture provided a complete record of the behavioral data, and allowed for synchronization of taps, audio, and EEG.

3 Analysis

To validate the tapping orchestra platform and synchronization paradigm, we demonstrate the reliability of behavioral synchronization measures and neural entrainment (ASSR) responses. These metrics establish that our novel multi-person setup successfully captures coordination patterns across varying group sizes and reliably measures EEG responses. Comprehensive analyses addressing specific hypotheses about group coordination mechanisms are beyond this validation study's scope.

3.1.1 Statistical Software

MATLAB (version R2023b, Mathworks, 2023) was used for initial preprocessing and calculation of dependent variables. Subsequent processing and statistical analyses were conducted using R (version 4.5.2R *Programming Language*) in the Visual Studio Code programming environment (version 1.109.2, Microsoft, 2024). Mixed-effects models were fit using the *glmmTMB* package (version 1.1.14, McGillicuddy et al., 2025). Model fits were compared using -2 log likelihood comparisons (via the *anova* function in the *stats* package in base R). Type III ANOVA-style effects and interactions from best-fitted models were obtained using the *Anova* function in the *car* package (version 3.1-3, Fox & Weisberg, 2019), which

returns likelihood-ratio chi-square tests for generalized linear model effects and interactions. Post-hoc comparisons were conducted using estimated marginal means via the *emmeans* package (version 2.0.1, Lenth & Piaskowski, 2025). For multiple comparisons, *p*-values were adjusted using the multivariate *t*-distribution method to control family-wise error rate while accounting for the correlation structure between contrasts.

3.1.2 Preprocessing

Tapping data were recorded in a single log file during data acquisition and imported into MATLAB, where they were merged with EEG data structures using custom scripts. Tapping data for each trial were extracted for all participants, and data quality checks were performed to identify taps that occurred twice in association with the same pitch and missing taps, which were replaced with *NaN* values. Taps were temporally aligned between Leader-Follower pairs on each trial using a pitch-matching algorithm (see Section 3.2.1.3). This algorithm matched the pitch indices generated during online data acquisition, creating corresponding time-points where Followers produced the same pitch as the Leader. From these aligned taps, dependent measures (absolute and signed asynchrony) were computed on each trial for each Leader-Follower pair and exported to a CSV file for subsequent processing and statistical analysis in *R*.

3.1.3 Dependent Measures

Absolute asynchrony. Synchronization accuracy between group members was assessed by computing absolute asynchrony for each Leader-Follower pair on every trial. Absolute asynchrony was defined as the absolute value of the temporal difference between pitch-aligned taps, computed in samples, and converted to milliseconds. Lower absolute asynchrony values indicate smaller temporal offsets between taps (i.e., better synchronization), whereas higher values indicate larger temporal offsets (i.e., poorer synchronization).

Signed asynchrony. Dynamics of anticipation and lag between Leaders and Followers were assessed by computing signed asynchrony for each Leader-Follower pair on every trial. Signed asynchrony was defined as the signed temporal difference between pitch-aligned taps (Leader tap time – Follower tap time). Negative values indicate that the Leader tapped before the Follower (i.e., the Follower lagged), whereas positive values indicate that the Follower tapped before the Leader (i.e., the Follower anticipated).

3.1.3.1 Mixed effects models

We fit generalized linear mixed effects models (GLMMs) to estimate relationships between independent and dependent measures. Two sets of models were created: one for absolute asynchrony and one for signed asynchrony. Both sets shared the same fixed-effects structure and approach to comparing random effects structures, as described below.

Fixed effects. Both model sets included two fixed effects: (1) Serial position in the scale sequence (8 levels, within-participant); and (2) Group size (4-person/6-person/10-person, between-participant). All fixed effects were coded as factors, and all main effects and interactions were estimated using sum contrasts (*contr.sum*).

Random effects. For each model set, two random effects structures were compared. A base model (M0) included random intercepts for participant (1 | subject) and for leader identity nested within group size (1 | size:leader). A second model (M1) added a first-order autoregressive [AR(1)] correlation structure for serial position within participants [ar1(serial + 0 | subject)] to account for temporal autocorrelation across tones within each scale sequence. Models were compared using likelihood ratio tests via the *anova()* function. M1 was singular when predicting absolute asynchrony, indicating an overly complex random structure. Therefore, M0 was selected to predict both absolute and signed asynchrony to ensure equivalent random structures.

Distribution families. Due to the positive skew characteristic of absolute asynchronies, GLMMs for absolute asynchrony used a Gamma distribution with log link function [family = Gamma(link = "log")]. Standard linear mixed models (Gaussian distribution with identity link) were used for signed asynchronies, which exhibited distributions closer to normality.

Data preparation. Prior to fitting mixed effects models, we applied several data filtering steps. First, one trial from the six-person group in which participants did not follow task instructions was excluded. Second, the first and second repetitions were excluded to focus on stable performance periods (repetitions 3–20 were retained). Finally, outlier taps were identified and removed based on absolute asynchronies that fell outside the 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles computed across all recorded taps in the main group synchronization task.

3.2 EEG data

The focus of the present analysis is to validate the EEG setup using data from the ASSR paradigm. Analysis of EEG data from the tapping study is beyond the scope of this paper.

First, the EEG recordings were re-referenced to the average of the M1 and M2 electrode signals. The data were then bandpass filtered between 2 and 100 Hz, followed by a 50 Hz notch filter to attenuate powerline interference. After filtering, the signals were segmented into 1-second epochs aligned with the stimulus based on the trigger signal. FFT was applied to each epoch, and the noise level in the epoch was estimated as the root mean square (RMS) amplitude from 35 to 45 Hz, excluding the 40 Hz bin. The 200 epochs with the lowest noise level was then selected, and the ASSR waveform was obtained by weighted averaging in the time domain, as described by John et al. (John et al., 2001). The weight of each the epoch was based on the estimated noise of the epoch. For signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) analysis, an FFT was applied to the averaged waveform.

Signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the measured ASSR was computed to evaluate the presence of a neurophysiological response to the auditory stimulus. The ASSR signal was defined as the spectral power at 40 Hz, while noise was estimated as the average spectral power in the surrounding frequency band from 35 to 45 Hz, excluding the 40 Hz bin. Statistical evaluation of ASSR detectability was performed using an *F*-test based on the ratio of signal to noise power, as described by Picton et al. (Picton et al., 2003). The analysis described above were performed in

MATLAB 2023b (Mathworks, 2023) using a combination of custom scripts and functions from the EEGLAB toolbox.

4 Results

4.1 Behavioural

4.1.1 Absolute asynchrony

Figure 5. Group synchronization. Absolute (Panel A) and signed (Panel B) estimated marginal mean tone onset asynchronies for each group size across sequence positions of the simple melody (8-tone musical scale).

Main effects & interactions. Figure 5A displays mean absolute asynchronies for each group size and serial position in the melody. There was a marginally significant main effect of *Group size* on absolute asynchrony, $\chi^2(2) = 5.417, p = .066$, a significant main effect of *Serial Position* (of

tone in scale sequence), $\chi^2(7) = 1704.694, p < .0001$, and a significant interaction between *Group size x Serial position* (of tone in the scale sequence), $\chi^2(14) = 202.784, p < .0001$. Contrasts were conducted to identify underlying sources of the interaction.

Table 1. Pairwise comparisons by group size and serial position in melody. Corrected pairwise comparisons for Absolute Asynchrony at serial positions 1-8. Significance levels below 0.05 are bolded and indicated with asterisks.

Group Sizes	1		2		3		4		5		6		7		8	
	z-ratio	p	z-ratio	p	z-ratio	p	z-ratio	p								
4 vs. 6	-1.629	0.234	-1.370	0.357	-0.881	0.652	-0.667	0.783	-0.152	0.987	0.014	1.000	-0.077	0.997	-0.490	0.876
4 vs. 10	-1.318	0.385	-1.043	0.550	-1.982	0.117	-2.176	0.075	-2.347	0.050	-2.596	0.026	-2.347	0.050	-2.921	0.010
6 vs. 10	0.566	0.838	0.544	0.849	-1.099	0.515	-1.579	0.255	-2.405	0.043	-2.883	0.011	-2.495	0.034	-2.621	0.024

Bold p-values indicate $p < 0.05$

Follow-up contrasts. To probe the two-way *Serial Position x Group Size* interaction, custom contrasts were first implemented testing whether asynchrony at Tone 1 (immediately following silence) differed from all subsequent tones (Tones 2–8) as a function of Group Size. These contrasts confirmed that asynchrony was significantly increased at Tone 1 across all group sizes (all p 's $< .005$). Subsequent contrasts between group sizes at all serial positions are shown in Table 1.

4.1.2 Signed asynchrony

Main effects & interactions. Figure 5B displays mean signed asynchronies for each group size and serial position in the melody. There was a marginally significant main effect of *Group size* on absolute asynchrony, $\chi^2(2) = 5.817, p = .0545$, a significant main effect of *Serial Position* (of tone in scale sequence), $\chi^2(7) = 6445.700, p < .0001$, and a significant interaction between *Group size x Serial position* (of tone in the scale sequence), $\chi^2(14) = 239.069, p < .0001$. Contrasts were conducted to identify underlying sources of the interaction.

Table 2. Pairwise comparisons by group size and serial position in melody for signed asynchrony. Corrected pairwise comparisons for signed asynchrony at serial positions 1-8. Significance levels below 0.05 are bolded and indicated with asterisks.

Group Sizes	1		2		3		4		5		6		7		8	
	z-ratio	p	z-ratio	p	z-ratio	p	z-ratio	p								
4 vs. 6	2.242	0.064	1.669	0.217	0.343	0.937	-0.257	0.964	-0.503	0.870	-0.174	0.983	-0.170	0.984	0.298	0.952
4 vs. 10	0.912	0.633	-0.173	0.984	-1.261	0.417	-2.253	0.063	-2.504	0.033	-2.363	0.048	-2.071	0.096	-2.343	0.050
6 vs. 10	-1.770	0.180	-2.259	0.062	-1.823	0.162	-2.179	0.075	-2.151	0.080	-2.400	0.043	-2.082	0.094	-2.964	0.009

Bold p-values indicate $p < 0.05$

Follow-up contrasts. To probe the two-way *Serial Position x Group Size* interaction, custom contrasts were first implemented testing whether asynchrony at Tone 1 (immediately following silence) differed from all subsequent tones (Tones 2–8) as a function of Group Size. These contrasts confirmed that asynchrony was significantly increased at Tone 1 across all group sizes

(all p 's < .005). Subsequent contrasts between group sizes at each serial position are shown in Table 2.

4.1.3 Reliability of behavioral measurements

Intraclass correlation coefficients (ICCs) were computed for both signed and absolute asynchronies to assess the proportion of variance in asynchrony attributable to differences between clusters (leaders and participants) versus within-cluster variation. High ICCs indicate that much of the variance is explained by systematic differences between clusters, whereas low ICCs indicate that most variance occurs within clusters (i.e., observation-level variation) rather than between them.

For the absolute asynchrony model, the ICC for leaders nested within group size was 0.079, and the ICC for participants was 0.080. For the signed asynchrony model, the ICC for leaders nested within group size was 0.085, and the ICC for participants was 0.093. These low ICCs indicate that minimal variance was attributable to systematic differences between leaders or participants. Instead, variance was primarily explained by the experimental fixed factors — specifically, the serial position and group size effects and their interaction in addition to possible trial-level variance.

4.1.4 ASSR

The ASSR was calculated for 19 participants (data from one participant was not available due to technical recording error). Figure 6 (a) shows the power spectrum of the time-averaged data for electrodes Cz and Fz, with a clear and statistically significant first and second harmonic response at 40 and 80 Hz, respectively. Figure 6 (b) shows the percentage of ASSR recording with a statistically significant response ($p < 0.05$) for each electrode location on the scalp for the average M1 and M2 reference configuration.

Figure 6. (a): Power spectrum of the grand average ASSR for electrodes Cz and Fz. Faded lines are individual ASSR recordings (b): Number of recordings with a significant ASSR response ($p < 0.05$) at each electrode location, excluding EOG and reference electrodes.

5 Discussion

In this paper we presented “The Tapping Orchestra”, a platform for measuring group synchrony at the levels of brain and behavior. The orchestra was developed to extend classic paradigms of dyadic synchrony (joint rhythmic finger-tapping, Keller et al., 2014) to larger groups, enabling systematic comparison.

5.1 *Technical implementation & validation*

We first described key considerations for implementing group synchrony measurement platforms and illustrated how these considerations were applied in “The Tapping Orchestra”. Specifically, we highlighted the importance of developing low-latency platforms for measuring tapping synchrony, considering (1) intra-subject action-sound latencies, (2) inter-subject tapping latencies, and (3) equipment synchronization.

Through carefully conducted timing tests, we demonstrated action-sound latencies on the order of milliseconds, thus lower than the sampling period of a standard EEG sampling rate at 500 Hz. Processing of taps were perfectly synchronized (zero-latency), and a constant offset between sampling clocks of the equipment were observed, allowing for correction if needed.

Together, these tests not only validate our own platform but also illustrate how to conduct appropriate timing tests for group recordings. These tests are critical to implement (though not typically reported in the literature) and can be conducted regardless of the recording modality (EEG, physiology, etc.). The critical feature is to obtain sample-level synchronization between equipment, to allow time-domain analysis across modalities (Kappel et al., 2025). This can be obtained with a common trigger signal, in this case created by the Bela and transmitted to all additional recording devices (EEG) via cables. Kappel et al. describes additional methods which can be used to temporally alignment data both online and offline (Kappel et al., 2025).

5.2 *Empirical validation through adaptation of dyadic paradigm*

We empirically validated "The Tapping Orchestra" platform by adapting a dyadic synchronization paradigm (Zamm et al., 2021) to test how synchronization dynamics generalize to larger groups. Below we describe implications of validation study findings.

5.2.1 *Generalization of dyadic synchronization dynamics*

The validation study confirmed that dyadic synchronization dynamics indeed generalize to larger groups. Coordination breakdowns following silences in interaction (unmetered silences between musical sequences) occurred in all group sizes, replicating original dyadic findings. Specifically, synchronization decreased (larger absolute asynchronies) immediately following silences.

Moreover, silences destabilized prediction-response dynamics in Followers. Signed tone onset asynchronies showed that Followers typically predicted Leaders during continuous rhythm,

which is characteristic of stable synchronization (Aschersleben, 2002). However, after silences, Followers temporarily switched from prediction to response. Thus, rhythmic destabilization from unmetered pauses reduced synchronization accuracy across group sizes, supporting the essential role of rhythm in coordination (for a review, see Keller et al., 2014). Furthermore, rhythmic destabilization appears to increase reliance on Leader-Follower roles, suggesting these become most critical when rhythmic scaffolding is absent.

We also examined whether these established synchronization dynamics were modulated by group size. Findings revealed that all groups were equally perturbed by silence: synchronization accuracy decreased and Followers responded rather than anticipated Leaders. However, from the middle of the melody onward, during continuous rhythm production, group size effects emerged. Specifically, larger groups (6- and 10-person) displayed significantly worse synchronization accuracy after recovering from silences, which may be driven by group size differences in baseline synchronization. Moreover, 10-person groups showed significantly more positive signed asynchronies than smaller groups during continuous rhythm, indicating that Followers in the largest groups anticipated the Leader more, though this effect was not consistent across serial positions.

Summary. Together, findings from the validation study underscore rhythm's essential and universal role in scaffolding multi-person coordination. The core synchronization dynamics—disruption at silence followed by recovery during continuous rhythm—generalize robustly across group sizes from dyads to 10-person ensembles. This suggests that the mechanisms supporting interpersonal synchronization, including predictive timing and leader-follower roles, operate similarly regardless of ensemble size, at least within the range tested here. However, effects of group size on synchronization accuracy during continuous rhythm point to the importance of investigating groups of diverse size.

5.2.2 Reliability of synchronization measures

Low intraclass correlation coefficients observed for both statistical models of synchronization (absolute and signed) provide important validation of behavioral measures. Most critically, the low ICC for participants after controlling for effects of leader nested within group indicates that the synchronization patterns observed—including disruption at silence and recovery during continuous rhythm—were highly consistent across individuals. This consistency suggests that the experimental paradigm successfully isolates fundamental mechanisms of interpersonal coordination, rather than capturing participant-specific strategies or abilities.

Together, these findings indicate that variance in synchronization was primarily driven by experimental manipulations (serial position, group size, and their interaction) rather than by individual differences. This pattern validates the paradigm's ability to systematically probe the role of rhythmic structure in multi-person coordination and supports the generalizability of the observed effects beyond the specific individuals tested.

5.2.3 Validation of group EEG recordings

Validation of EEG setup was performed through analyses of EEG recordings of the ASSR from all participants. In the context of the present study, the ASSR was used to estimate whether the electrode-skin interface of an electrode was good enough to measure a neural response.

The results show a statistically significant response in all recordings for most central and frontal electrode locations, whereas the percentage of significant recordings is lower in the occipital and temporal regions. This corresponds well with the spatial distribution of the ASSR previously reported for a similar modulation frequency and reference configuration (Christensen et al., 2021; Herdman et al., 2002). In addition to these distribution related observations, the lower percentage of significant ASSR recordings at the rim of the cap might be explained by a higher sensitivity to motion artifacts for these electrode locations.

Generally, ASSR analysis shows high data quality. For future analysis, additional reference configurations could be explored to get a more complete image of the response at the temporal and occipital regions.

5.2.4 Limitations & practical considerations

It should be noted that the current study measured relatively few groups, though computing synchronization pairwise (between Leader-Follower pairs within each group) enabled numerous repeated measures. Linear mixed effects models accommodated variable group sizes and nested effects of pairs within groups, partially mitigating sample size concerns. Nevertheless, larger samples are needed to draw stronger conclusions.

Sample size poses a major practical obstacle for group research: obtaining sufficient groups (when group is the unit of analysis) requires funding far exceeding typical single-person or dyadic studies. Similarly, acquiring sufficient recording devices—behavioral, EEG, physiological—presents substantial financial barriers. Statistical and practical solutions are essential to make group-level social neuroscience accessible to researchers without exceptionally large grants.

6 Conclusions & Future Directions

The current platform and findings demonstrate the feasibility of scaling beyond the dyad at both methodological and paradigmatic levels, marking an important step in the evolution from "two-brain" (Konvalinka & Roepstorff, 2012) to "many-brain" approaches to interpersonal coordination. The robust generalization of rhythm-based coordination mechanisms across group sizes, combined with group size effects on synchronization, validates this approach and suggests these dynamics will extend effectively to new contexts.

Taken together, "The Tapping Orchestra" opens exciting possibilities for testing the generalizability of dyadic synchrony models in larger ensembles, comparing coordination dynamics across musicians and non-musicians of different ages, and exploring developmental

trajectories of group coordination. Beyond merely scaling dyadic paradigms, this platform enables investigation of coordination mechanisms that arise specifically in group interactions, which are rarely symmetric and may depend on the group composition.

More generally, group paradigms allow researchers to investigate how individuals negotiate leader-follower roles or relative action contributions when some members share prior social affiliation while others do not (Li et al., 2025); how asymmetric expertise influences collective timing; or how coordination unfolds when some participants' actions have less influence on the rest of the group. In musical ensembles, similar questions arise regarding how musicians with different levels or types of experience maintain coordination (e.g., Wing et al., 2014), how leadership emerges during sections without a clear rhythmic structure (D'Ausilio et al., 2012), or how smaller subsets of performers align with one another within a larger ensemble. Such questions are difficult to address in dyadic designs because they depend on the presence of multiple simultaneous partners whose relationships and abilities may differ (Gordon, 2025). Studying coordination in groups therefore provides an opportunity to investigate how various interpersonal factors – such as interpersonal relationships, expertise, and interaction roles – contribute to the behavioral and neural mechanisms underlying collective action.

7 CRediT statement

A.Z. (conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, funding acquisition, investigation, methodology, project administration, software, resources, validation, visualization, writing – original draft, writing – reviewing and editing)

S.L.K. (conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, funding acquisition, investigation, methodology, project administration, software, resources, validation, visualization, writing – original draft, writing – reviewing and editing)

A.D. (formal analysis, writing – reviewing and editing)

S.D. (conceptualization, writing – reviewing and editing)

I.K. (conceptualization, writing – reviewing and editing)

8 Funding & acknowledgments

This work was supported by Seed Project Grant (26245) from the Interacting Minds Center at Aarhus University and Center for Ear-EEG (33256), Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Aarhus University. The authors would like to thank Jacopo Comoglio, Bowen Duan and Luke Ring for their help with data collection, and Professor Preben Kidmose for contributing input on the project.

9 Data Statement

Data can be shared upon reasonable requests to the corresponding authors.

10 Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process.

During the preparation of this manuscript, the author used generative AI (Claude Sonnet 4, ChatGPT5) to clarify and shorten text and to develop and optimize parts of the analysis and plotting code. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

11 Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

12 References

- Abalde, S. F., Rigby, A., Keller, P. E., & Novembre, G. (2024). A framework for joint music making: Behavioral findings, neural processes, and computational models. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2024.105816>
- Aschersleben, G. (2002). Temporal control of movements in sensorimotor synchronization. *Brain and cognition*, 48(1), 66-79.
- Christensen, C. B., Lunner, T., Harte, J. M., Rank, M. L., & Kidmose, P. (2021). Chirp-evoked auditory steady-state response: The effect of repetition rate. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, 69(2), 689-699.
- D'Ausilio, A., Badino, L., Li, Y., Tokay, S., Craighero, L., Canto, R., Aloimonos, Y., & Fadiga, L. (2012). Leadership in orchestra emerges from the causal relationships of movement kinematics. *PLoS one*, 7(5), e35757.
- Demos, & Palmer. (2023). Social and nonlinear dynamics unite: musical group synchrony. *Trends Cogn Sci*, 27(11), 1008-1018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2023.05.005>
- Demos, A. P., & Palmer, C. (2023). Musical synchrony, dynamical systems and information processing: Merger or redundancy? *Trends Cogn Sci*, 27(12), 1107-1108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2023.08.015>
- Demos, A. P., & Palmer, C. (2023). Social and nonlinear dynamics unite: musical group synchrony. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 27(11). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2023.05.005>
- Fox, J., & Weisberg, S. (2019). *An R Companion to Applied Regression* (Third edition ed.). Sage. <https://www.john-fox.ca/Companion/>
- Galambos, R., Makeig, S., & Talmachoff, P. J. (1981). A 40-Hz auditory potential recorded from the human scalp. *Proceedings of the national academy of sciences*, 78(4), 2643-2647.
- Gordon, I. (2025). Interpersonal synchrony research in human groups. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 19(6), e70068.
- Grahn, J. A., & Rowe, J. B. (2009). Feeling the beat: premotor and striatal interactions in musicians and nonmusicians during beat perception. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 29(23), 7540-7548.
- Heggli, O. A., Konvalinka, I., Kringelbach, M. L., & Vuust, P. (2021). A metastable attractor model of self–other integration (MEAMSO) in rhythmic synchronization. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 376(1835).
- Herdman, A. T., Lins, O., Van Roon, P., Stapells, D. R., Scherg, M., & Picton, T. W. (2002). Intracerebral sources of human auditory steady-state responses. *Brain topography*, 15(2), 69-86.
- Hoehl, S., Fairhurst, M., & Schirmer, A. (2021). Interactional synchrony: signals, mechanisms and benefits. *Social Cognitive and Affective Neuroscience*, 16(1-2), 5-18. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scan/nsaa024>
- John, M. S., Dimitrijevic, A., & Picton, T. W. (2001). Weighted averaging of steady-state responses. *Clinical neurophysiology*, 112(3), 555-562.
- Kappel, S. L., Jørgensen, A. N., & Kidmose, P. (2025). Temporal Synchronization of Multimodal Hyperscanning Recordings: Challenges, Methodologies, and Best Practices. 2025 47th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC),

- Kappel, S. L., & Kidmose, P. (2022). Characterization of dry-contact EEG electrodes and an empirical comparison of Ag/AgCl and IrO₂ electrodes. 2022 44th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine & Biology Society (EMBC),
- Kappel, S. L., Makeig, S., & Kidmose, P. (2019). Ear-EEG forward models: improved head-models for ear-EEG. *Frontiers in neuroscience*, *13*, 943.
- Keller, P. E. (2023). Integrating theory and models of musical group interaction. *Trends Cogn Sci*, *27*(12), 1105-1106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2023.07.008>
- Keller, P. E., Novembre, G., & Hove, M. J. (2014). Rhythm in joint action: psychological and neurophysiological mechanisms for real-time interpersonal coordination. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, *369*(1658), 20130394.
- Konvalinka, I., & Roepstorff, A. (2012). The two-brain approach: how can mutually interacting brains teach us something about social interaction? *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, *6*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2012.00215>
- Konvalinka, I., Sebanz, N., & Knoblich, G. (2023). The role of reciprocity in dynamic interpersonal coordination of physiological rhythms. *Cognition*, *230*, 105307.
- Konvalinka, I., Sebanz, N., & Knoblich, G. (2025). The social, decoupled self: interpersonal synchronization of breathing alters intrapersonal cardiorespiratory coupling. *bioRxiv*, 2025.2009. 2029.679159.
- Konvalinka, I., Vuust, P., Roepstorff, A., & Frith, C. D. (2010). Follow you, follow me: continuous mutual prediction and adaptation in joint tapping. *Quarterly journal of experimental psychology*, *63*(11), 2220-2230.
- Lenth, R., & Piaskowski, J. (2025). *emmeans: Estimated Marginal Means, aka Least-Squares Means*. In R package. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=emmeans>
- Li, Q., Dabranau, A., Kompatsiari, K., & Konvalinka, I. (2025). Friendship modulates physical effort and neural dynamics during group coordination in shared social networks. *bioRxiv*, 2025.2012. 2030.695445.
- Marois, R., & Ivanoff, J. (2005). Capacity limits of information processing in the brain. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, *9*(6), 296-305.
- Mathworks, I. (2023). *MATLAB*. In (Version 2023b) <https://www.mathworks.com/content/dam/mathworks/mathworks-dot-com/support/sysreq/files/system-requirements-release-2023b-supported-compilers.pdf>
- McGillycuddy, M., Warton, D. I., Popovic, G., & Bolker, B. M. (2025). Parsimoniously Fitting Large Multivariate Random Effects in glmmTMB. *Journal of Statistical Software*, *112*(1), 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v112.i01>
- Microsoft, C. (2024). *Visual Studio Code*. In Microsoft Corporation. <https://code.visualstudio.com/>
- [Record #37 is using a reference type undefined in this output style.]
- Palmer, C. (1997). Music performance. *Annual review of psychology*, *48*(1), 115-138.
- Picton, T. W., John, M. S., Dimitrijevic, A., & Purcell, D. (2003). Human auditory steady-state responses: Respuestas auditivas de estado estable en humanos. *International journal of audiology*, *42*(4), 177-219.
- R Programming Language*. In. (Version 4.5.2) R Core Team <https://cran.r-project.org/bin/windows/base/>
- Repp, B. H. (2006). Musical synchronization. *Music, motor control, and the brain*, 55-76.
- Repp, B. H., & Su, Y.-H. (2013). Sensorimotor synchronization: A review of recent research (2006–2012). *Psychonomic bulletin & review*, *20*(3), 403-452.

- Schilbach, L., Timmermans, B., Reddy, V., Costall, A., Bente, G., Schlicht, T., & Vogeley, K. (2013). Toward a second-person neuroscience. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 36(4), 393-414. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0140525x12000660>
- Sebanz, N., Bekkering, H., & Knoblich, G. (2006). Joint action: bodies and minds moving together. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 10(2), 70-76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2005.12.009>
- Sebanz, N., & Knoblich, G. (2021). Progress in Joint-Action Research. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 30(2), 138-143. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721420984425>
- Tamminen, K. A., Danyluck, C., Bonk, D., & Chen, R. (2023). Syncing to perform? A naturalistic uncontrolled prospective case study of emotional and physiological synchrony in a team of male volleyball athletes. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 41(11), 1033-1046. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2023.2259205>
- Wing, A. M., Endo, S., Bradbury, A., & Vorberg, D. (2014). Optimal feedback correction in string quartet synchronization. *Journal of The Royal Society Interface*, 11(93).
- Zamm, A., Debener, S., Konvalinka, I., Sebanz, N., & Knoblich, G. (2021). The Sound of Silence: An EEG study of how musicians time pauses in individual and joint music performance. *Social Cognitive and Affective Neuroscience*.